

Fields without a trap crop, but sprayed with cypermethrin, were the treated control. Unsprayed fields without a trap crop were the untreated control.

Plot size was 11 × 17 m. Each treatment was replicated four times.

At 65 DT, RTV incidence was significantly higher in the untreated control than in trap or insecticide-treated fields (Table 1). Relatively higher nymphal and adult GLH populations were recorded.

Yields were significantly higher in trap and insecticide-treated fields than in the untreated control (Table 2). Although yield was highest in insecticide-treated fields, the cost of cypermethrin lowered net gain. Limited insecticide use also conserves natural enemies of rice pests. □

Table 2. Value of yields with and without trap crop after deducting cost of cypermethrin^a. IRRI, May–Sep 1986.

Treatment	Area (ha)		Combined yield (t/ha)	Value of yield ^b (\$/ha)	Cypermethrin applied ^c (liters/ha)	Cost ^d (\$/ha)	Net value (\$/ha)
	Trap crop	Main crop					
2-row trap crop and main crop	0.074	0.926	4.5 a	787.50	0.592	14.21	713.29 a
3-row trap crop and main crop	0.109	0.891	4.2 a	735.00	0.872	20.93	714.07 a
4-row trap crop and main crop	0.144	0.856	4.4 a	770.00	1.152	27.65	742.35 a
Treated control	0	1.000	4.9 a	857.50	8.000	192.00	665.50 ab
Untreated control	0	1.000	3.3 b	577.50	0	0	577.50 b

^a Av of 4 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^b US\$ = P20; value of rice (NFA price) = \$0.175/kg. ^c Eight applications to trap crop rows and treated control plots @ 0.05 kg ai/ha per treatment. ^d Cost of cypermethrin Jul 1986 = \$24/liter.

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Rice thrips *Stenchaetothrips biformis* (Bagnall) effect on yield

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We evaluated thrips damage and subsequent yield in highly susceptible variety Bg 94-1. We assumed that natural thrips infestation would be uniform over all plots, if not controlled. Carbofuran at 1 kg ai/ha was used in an

experiment in late Nov 1983. A second experiment used different insecticides. Damage was rated according to the *Standard evaluation system for rice* 3–4 wk after sowing. After assessment, the plants were fully protected from other pest attacks.

In carbofuran-treated plots, thrips damage was rated as 1; in untreated

control plots, 7–9. Average grain yield in treated plots (3.34 t/ha) was significantly different from that in the untreated plots (2.34 t/ha) at 5% level of probability. Plots treated with different chemicals had a control rating of 1 for all but triazophos, which rated 5; untreated plots rated 7 (see figure). Yields varied. □

Thrips damage and rice yield under chemical control, Sri Lanka, 1983.

Influence of age of crop and time of planting on gall midge (GM) incidence

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Rice GM *Orseolia oryzivora* is a serious

pest of wet season (WS) rice at Edozhigi, an irrigated area in Nigeria. The rainy season in this area is Jun-Oct and farmers transplant in Sep.

We measured GM incidence on FARO 27 and FARO 29 in the 1985 WS on samples of 50 hills/variety, replicated 3 times. Percentage of silvershoots was calculated as the ratio

GM incidence by age of rice crop. Edozhigi, Nigeria, 1985 wet season.

Days after transplanting	Silvershoots ^a (%)		
	FARO 27	FARO 29	Mean
30	13.8 (21.6)	11.8 (17.4)	12.8
40	15.4 (22.6)	18.0 (25.1)	16.7
50	14.5 (21.7)	18.2 (25.2)	16.4
60	7.9 (16.1)	15.3 (22.9)	11.6
70	7.7 (16.0)	10.4 (18.6)	9.1
LSD (0.05)	10.2	6.7	

^a Figures in parentheses are transformed angular values, LSDs refer to them.